

UNIVERSITY OF GRANADA

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In Spain, gender-based violence (GBV) has been addressed institutionally by higher education institutions (HEIs) for over a decade, fundamentally as a result of the obligations created in this regard by various national laws, such as Organic Act No 3/2007 on Effective Equality between Women and Men, Act No. 14/2011 on Science, Technology and Innovation, and Law 1/2004 Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence. Although this act does not make specific detailed reference to universities, it does raise the issue of education and awareness and establishes that both the State and the Autonomous Communities, within the scope of their respective powers, will adapt their regulations to the provisions contained in the Law. As a result, all Autonomous Communities have adopted their own laws against GBV. Only the Law 17/2020 of the Autonomous Community of Catalonia mentions specifically GBV in Universities.

In the past five years, however, the treatment of GBV has been marked by a surge in awareness of its structural rather than individual nature and has therefore seen the further adoption and/or renewal of institutional policies aimed at addressing GBV in an integrated manner through measures of prevention, detection, investigation, prosecution, partnership, protection, and service provision.

The most common instruments used to address GBV in HEIs (prescribed by law) are Institutional Equality Plans, which increasingly include GBV among their other equality aims, and dedicated Protocols, which address one or more forms of GBV.

Over the past five years there has also been a proliferation of other types of action to address GBV at the institutional level in HEIs. Examples are the creation of specialised units, the integration of GBV into university curricula and research, the development of awareness-raising and training, the publication of statements, and the creation of protection mechanisms, services, and partnerships designed to promote an equal and non-violent environment and prevent and combat GBV in HEIs. In addition, GBV has been increasingly addressed by umbrella organisations such as the Network of Gender Equality Units (RUIGEU) and the Conference of Rectors (CRUE), which have issued statements to show their commitment to the elimination of GBV in HEIs. A defining feature of all these is that they have widened their subjective and material scope beyond the earlier focus on women and sexual and sex-based harassment. There is now a focus on other vulnerable groups, especially gender and sexual minorities, through the increasing adoption of an intersectional perspective, and on other forms of GBV, most notably online forms of GBV and sexual violence.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University of Granada (UGR) has two policies addressing GBV at the institutional level. The II Equality Plan 2020-2024 of the UGR addresses harassment and gender violence, along with other equality objectives, in reference to the specific forms outlined in the second document, which is the Protocol against harassment.

In both policies, the main responsible actor is the Equality and Conciliation Unit of the university, while the Protocol also indicates the Office of Prevention and Response to Harassment created within it, and the university ombudsperson, the Inspection of Services, and the dean, the latter in particular in relation to sanctions.

URLs

- › II Equality Plan 2020-2024 of the UGR: https://unidadigualdad.ugr.es/pages/iiplandeigualdad_1/
- › UGR's Protocol for the Prevention and Response against Harassment: http://mide.ugr.es/pages/banners_doc/protocolougrprevencionyrespuestaanteelacoso/

Entry into force: The Protocol against Gender Violence entered into force in 2018 and the third Plan for Equality of Women and Men in 2019.

TRAINING

The Equality Plan envisions the planning, design, execution, and evaluation of training activities with a gender and feminist perspective coordinated by the Equality Unit and aimed at the entire university community and at the prevention and detection of gender violence and harassment and response to them and LGTB-phobic violence.

The Protocol distinguishes between primary and secondary prevention measures. Primary measures include, among other activities, trainings developed to transmit specific knowledge and skills on issues related to bullying and aimed at specific groups in the university community. The training will be included in general training activities on equality and actions focused on bullying and harassment.

In 2020, the UGR, with funding from the Women's Institute of Andalucía, created the University Network against Gender Violence, through which students and staff are trained in specialised protocols and techniques to act as agents and to sensitise, detect, and act against GBV. The training takes place online, separately for students and staff, in five sessions focused on providing techniques to attend to victims and raise awareness.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

The UGR offers courses, like the one offered in collaboration with the Equality Commission of the Faculty of Health Sciences of Melilla, a 30-hour training course on sensitisation towards gender violence among university students, aimed at raising awareness on GBV, with a focus on gender and sexual violence. The course was held virtually in March 2021 and was free and attendance was recognised with 2 ECTS. Furthermore, a study called 'The Prevalence and Characteristics of

Sexual Harassment among Students, PDI, and PAS of the University of Granada' was conducted during the academic year 2019-2020, and common lines of work on GBV were established with the Government Sub-delegation on GBV, through which the UGR carries out projects that are subsidised with funding from the Andalusian Institute for Women and the State Pact against Gender Violence.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies combined address **seven** forms of violence out of 11:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

Both policies refer to physical, psychological violence and gender-based harassment. In addition, the Protocol addresses cases of sexual harassment, stalking, including their online forms and another form, that is, gender-based bullying.

7Ps covered: Together the two policies cover all **7Ps**, namely: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, partnership and policies.

The Equality Plan focuses on prevention, protection, the provision services, and the creation of partnerships. The Protocol covers all 7Ps except for provision of services and partnerships.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: Both policies combined address academic staff, non-academic staff, and students. The Protocol also covers other groups such as students in incoming mobility programmes, personnel who have a link with the UGR through the professional services developed at the university, and any person included in the previous sections whose relationship with the University of Granada has ended (under any legal form) who claim to have experienced harassment and demand action in reference to this Protocol within one year of the date that their relationship with the university ended.

Specific vulnerable groups: International students, LGBTQIA+ staff and students. The Equality Plan specifically mentions LGBT persons in the axis dedicated to training on GBV, though not in the one dedicated to harassment and GBV specifically, where it does, however, mention the need to guarantee intersectional and comprehensive attention, promoting tools that channel and solve the cases presented.

Intersectionality addressed: Yes, both policy documents address intersectionality. The Equality Plan includes LGBT people among its target groups and in relation to gender violence it establishes the need to guarantee that intersectional and comprehensive attention is paid to situations of gender violence, harassment, or any type of discrimination in the university community, promoting tools that channel and solve with due guarantees cases of such behaviour. Intersectionality is only explicitly referred to, however, in this case.

The Protocol specifically states that harassment can occur on the basis of multiple and simultaneous grounds. For this reason, it will be understood that harassment may be based on one or more grounds and includes unwanted conduct related to racial or ethnic origin, religion or beliefs, functional diversity, or sexual diversity within the definition of discriminatory moral harassment, and the Protocol explicitly mentions students in incoming mobility programmes as covered by this document.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Protocol refers to witnesses twice. First in relation to the situations that render cases of harassment particularly serious, with reference to the exertion of pressure or coercion against them, and second in relation to prohibiting retaliation against persons who appear as witnesses or otherwise participate in a formal or informal harassment proceeding under the terms provided in the applicable regulations is expressly prohibited.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Protocol addresses the person allegedly responsible for the conduct related to the harassment or aggressor in relation to the procedures and sanctions specified below.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. The Protocol establishes that, within the Equality Observatory of the UGR, a Technical Commission for Monitoring the Harassment Protocol will be created to prepare statistics and reports on all the actions carried out by the different structures of the UGR and especially those directly involved in the response and in bullying prevention. The statistics and reports on the different actions and cases remain anonymous at all times. The objective of this information is to improve the response to and prevention of bullying. The statistics will annually refer to each academic year, without prejudice to the partial studies that can be made on issues or situations and may be of interest for preventing and responding to harassment. The reports corresponding to each academic year are presented to the Equality Observatory and to the Governing Council. The management of the knowledge obtained through the actions of the Technical Committee for Monitoring the Harassment Protocol translate into proposals for the improvement and modification of the established prevention and response processes.

Evaluation: Yes. The Equality Plan provides for its evaluation across the three phases of its development: In the design phase the initial evaluation of the Plan will make it possible to determine whether the components it comprises (e.g. actions, resources, methodologies, schedule) are sufficient to meet its objectives and the needs of its recipients. In this way, improvements will be incorporated into the structure and design of the Equality Plan, permanently ensuring its sufficiency and relevance. In the implementation phase the evaluation of the implementation process of the Equality Plan and the different actions involved in this process will make it possible to analyse any discrepancies that exist between what has been planned and what is being implemented, ensure the proper use of resources, anticipate unplanned effects, and analyse the development of reprogrammed decisions. Based on the observed achievements and in a summary perspective, the evaluation will make it possible to further guide the process and detect new needs, and to evaluate the programme as a whole and assess its effectiveness, efficiency, effectiveness, and impact. However, the Equality Plan does not establish who is responsible or when or how often such evaluations will take place, or whether the evaluation feeds into quality assurance. In the year and a half that the Equality Plan has been in effect, it has been subject to general monitoring and evaluation by the Equality and Conciliation Unit. The Equality Observatory and related commissions have not yet been established.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. The Protocol against harassment sets out a step-by-step procedure that applies to everyone – **one procedure for all**.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, description of the investigation, responsible persons, outcomes, and sanctions.

The Protocol establishes a detailed institutional procedure for reporting, investigating, and sanctioning cases. It puts emphasis on the informal resolution of cases in order to avoid the heavy bureaucratisation of administrative procedure. Nevertheless, calls are being made for its update, for example, by the university's ombudsperson (Asensio, 2021).

Responsible persons: Two HR specialists work as harassment liaisons for staff – and in certain cases also students – in the university's HR Development and Occupational Wellbeing Unit, and one of them is the university's equality advisor. The OPRA, without prejudice to coordinated action with the Services Inspection and the university ombudsperson, is the body responsible for providing and coordinating comprehensive support to the victim.

Who to contact: The Student Union (HYY) has two harassment liaisons whom students can contact regarding harassment claims. The harassment liaisons are bound by the strictest confidentiality. The privacy of students and staff must be ensured in order to prevent discrimination and harassment.

Investigation procedure: At all times, the complainant will be informed of the progress of the Protocol procedure and will be offered care and protection against any negative consequences that the complainant may suffer. Regardless of what is considered necessary through the initiation and instruction of the formal disciplinary procedure, the OPRA may propose to the relevant bodies that protection measures be adopted to take into account the situation of the victims and the presence of risk factors.

Outcome, sanctions: Once an incident of harassment has been verified, the university, through the coordinated action of the OPRA and the competent centres and services in each case, will ensure that the victim receives care and attention, and will adopt, among others, the following support measures: it will (i) examine with necessary speed all information related to the victim's personal and professional situation; (ii) propose as many measures as deemed necessary to guarantee the comprehensive protection of the victim's health and especially their psychological health until they have fully recovered; (iii) advise the victim on obtaining health care and especially psychological and social care.

This document reflects the situation as of April 2022.

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